

THE FEDERATION OF ASIA-OCEANIA PERINATAL SOCIETIES

The FAOPS

Funiculus

Promoting Science & Art of Perinatology

ISSUE HIGHLIGHTS

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Ensuring Quality Perinatal Care

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25th Year of Publication

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From the Editor's Desk

Think Earth! Mothers, Babies, and Our Planet

Dear Readers,

The second edition of FAOPS Funiculus aims to highlight the activities conducted by our members. The first edition was published in 2023, in conjunction with the 2023 FAOPS held in Tokyo, Japan. Funiculus refers to the umbilical cord arising from the placental bed nourishing the baby, or of the stalks arising from the ovaries of plants reflecting our desire to grow and spread the knowledge of saving mothers and babies. We aim to fulfil one of the aims in the formation of the Federation of Asia Oceania Perinatal Societies or FAOPS, that is to promote the science and the art of perinatology in the region of Asia-Oceania.

In this issue's editorial as we meet during the 2024 Congress in Seoul, I wish to highlight an important issue that was raised during our recent Perinatal Society of Malaysia Congress – the health of our planet and the need to champion planetary health. In 2020, 35.3 million of 135 million live births (26.2%) are small vulnerable newborns (SVNs), i.e. (i) any baby born preterm, or (ii) SGA or (iii) both preterm and SGA. SVNs account for 99.5% of the world's 20 million LBW babies. Nearly two thirds (63.0%) of the world's term SGA newborns are in southern Asia (14.8 million, 40.9% of livebirths). Preterm birth rates have less regional variation but are also highest in southern Asia (13.2%).

Despite our efforts to provide quality maternal and newborn care, the rates of SVNs have not changed measurably in the past decade. Why? The missing link is likely the fact that our earth is ill. In 2022, 739 million children were exposed to high or extremely high water scarcity and 436 million children live in areas of high or extremely high water vulnerability. The odds of a preterm birth rises 1.05-fold per 1°C increase in temperature and 1.16-fold during heatwaves. In a meta-analysis (Chersich, 2020), higher temperature was associated with reduced birth weight in 18 of 28 studies, with considerable statistical heterogeneity.

Climate changes affect both the mother and her infant. The impacts can result from both direct (weather: heat waves, weather extremes, air quality: increasing CO₂ levels, rising sea levels, and indirect exposure patterns (water and food availability & quality, increasing allergens, environmental degradation). These affect both mother and baby via the epigenetic changes that

take place with alterations of DNA methylation/histone modification, a rise in presence of

endocrine-disrupting chemicals(EDC) such as synthetic chemicals and some pharmaceutical agents, and climate migration where groups of persons are obliged to leave their habitual place of residence, or choose to do so, either temporarily or permanently, within a State or across an international border.

We, the healthcare providers of Asia-Oceania region, can protect future generations by safeguarding the health of our planet. Planetary health threats related to maternal and child health can be addressed at policy level of each country. Countries can enhance social networks and increase awareness of the impact of planetary ill-health on overall perinatal health. We need to champion community programs, implement support programs during labor/childbirth, avoid breastfeeding disruption, address issues related to equitable food supply and ensure maternal feeding programs in compromised urban and rural settlements, to ensure that no mother, or baby is left behind – whether asylum seekers, refugees or internally displaced persons. We will need to think of what we can do together for the health of the mothers and our babies. The missing gap is the state of our planet, of climate change and wars. We need to do more for our future generation. The best steps are always taken tiny bits at a time – to improve ourselves to care for our planet right from our own doorsteps. We know we can.

I wish to sincerely thank the current FAOPS President, Professor Samuel Rajadurai, our FAOPS' past president Professor Satoshi Kusuda, the incoming president Professor Han Suk Kim, and all council members and country representatives who have motivated the publication of this issue.

Enjoy FAOPS 2024. Enjoy the FAOPS Funiculus!

The Editor

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The Objectives of FAOPS

The Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies (FAOPS) is a federation of national societies of perinatal and neonatal medicine in the geographical region of Asia and Oceania. It was established in 1978, on the same year of Alma Ata Declaration "Health for All by 2000". The first president was the late Geoffrey Thornburg, a reproductive physiologist from Australia, and the first secretariat was then established. From a 5-member federation, it has now been expanded to 20 members, where 17 are regular, and 3 are associate members.

The following are the objectives of the federation:

1. To promote the science and art of Perinatology.
2. To promote maternal welfare.
3. To promote fetal and neonatal well-being.
4. To maintain a liaison with other organizations or professions involved in Perinatology.
5. To promote cooperation and goodwill with international bodies involved in Perinatology.
6. To provide expert advice to governmental and other bodies pertaining to Perinatology.
7. To promote research and training in Perinatology.
8. To support country perinatal society guidelines on the ethical practice of the profession.

The Bye-Law Objectives

1. To promote, encourage and assist endeavours in all fields related to Perinatology.
2. To disseminate and communicate information on knowledge and skills concerning Perinatology, particularly those that present problems peculiar to the region.
3. To improve and uphold the highest standards of care in Perinatology.
4. To recommend common policies in these matters when requested by National Societies whenever joint action can or should be pursued in such matters.
5. To publish a Journal or to coordinate with other official Journals related to Perinatology.
6. To award scholarships, professorial lectures and prizes as determined from time to time.
7. To disseminate information relating to the objectives of the Federation to National Bodies, International Agencies, Foundations, and individuals with the Aim of furthering the Federation's interests.
8. To seek assistance, financial or otherwise, from National Bodies, International Agencies, Foundations or any other relevant party on matters of significance in maternal, perinatal and neonatal health.
9. To acquire, maintain and dispose of any assets to further the activities of the Federation.
10. To encourage and promote research and training in fields related to Perinatology.

Highlights from the FAOPS Eastern Region: Ensuring Quality Perinatal Care

By Jose B. Salazar, MD, MSPH, FPPS, FPSNBM

Professor and Head of Pediatrics, UERM Memorial Medical Center -College of Medicine, Philippines

Deputy General FAOPS Eastern Region

BACKGROUND

Strengthening perinatal care in Japan, Taiwan, the Philippines and Mongolia requires a focused strategy that considers the particular challenges in the delivery of maternal and neonatal care in each country. This includes adopting culturally appropriate strategies, enhancing access to high-quality maternal and neonatal care and encouraging teamwork among perinatal healthcare practitioners to ensure holistic support for mothers, infants and their families.

The highlights of the perinatal societies of the member countries of the FAOPS Eastern Region and key activities for 2023-2024 are as follows:

JAPAN

Japan Society of Perinatal and Neonatal Medicine

Prof. Mamoru Tanaka, MD, PhD

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Japan Society of Perinatal and Neonatal Medicine Highlights

- Superior perinatal care is supported by the perinatal system
- Perinatal system has developed into a research network and is useful for international research, which includes the following:
 - Transfer and referral system is also beneficial in disaster
 - Maternal and child health handbooks: record maternal and child health information
 - Perinatal medicine system: provided advanced perinatal care including comprehensive perinatal medical centers and regional perinatal centers
 - Neonatal Resuscitation Training: enhanced neonatal care
 - Declining perinatal mortality rates: achieved one of the lowest perinatal mortality rates among developed nations
 - Focus on perinatal mental health: made efforts to improve perinatal mental health care, including guidelines and financial resources,
 - Recognizing the importance of maternal emotional well-being.

Key Activities

2023

- HOST: 22nd Congress of the FAOPS: SGDs for Maternal and Neonatal Health for Asia-Oceania

Region

2024

- The 42nd Symposium of Japan Society of Perinatal and Neonatal Medicine. Theme' "New insights in perinatal nutrition and metabolism
- The 60th Annual Congress of Japan Society of Perinatal and Neonatal Medicine: Theme: SHIN: Perinatal and neonatal medicine

TAIWAN

Taiwan Society of Perinatology

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Taiwan Society of Perinatology Highlights

- Focused on maternal-fetal medicine
- Promotes education and training relevant to maternal and newborn health
- Proposes strategies and guidelines for high-risk pregnancy and standardized clinical assessment criteria which enhanced the quality of perinatal care
- Pushed for establishments of perinatal care centers
- Supported the development of a neonatal transport system
- Enhanced referral protocols: Quicker access to specialized care
- Improved the quality of neonatal care during transport and stabilization
- Holding symposium of perinatal medicine update for members and nurses engaging in high-risk pregnancy care every 3 months
- Holding the examination for specialist of maternal-fetal medicine every year
- Auditing the genetic disease inspection agency and Down syndrome screening quality.

Key Activities

2023

- Training for high-risk pregnancy care
- Seminar on maternal health protection strategies and management of preterm birth and postpartum hemorrhage and update
- Training course for senior laboratory personnel implementing and developing tests
- Perinatal infection and management of fetus with intrauterine growth restrictions and neonatal outcome
- Seminar on improving perinatal and perinatal maternal health: gestational hypertension, postpartum hemorrhage and management

2024

- Education program for high-risk pregnancy care
- Training for high-risk pregnancy care
- Expert meeting on Maternal and infant prevention guidelines for RSV in Taiwan
- Symposium on Management of Perinatal complication and concepts
- Annual meeting and academic symposium

MONGOLIA

Mongolia Perinatal Association

Prof. Gerelmaa Zagd

Mongolian National University of Medical Sciences

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Mongolia Perinatal Association Highlights

- Introduction of the Maternal and Child Health Handbook (2010): Improved antenatal care significantly
- Maternal, Child and Reproductive Health Programs (2017-2021) resulted in a notable decrease in maternal mortality
- Midwifery Development: Enhanced midwifery education and expanded the role of midwives to improve maternal and prenatal outcomes
- Primary Healthcare Reforms: emphasized preventive care and community based to maternal health
- Data Collection and Research: The Mongolia Social Indicator Sample Surveys (MSISS): Provided valuable data on reproductive health to improve programs aimed at improving maternal and child health

Key Activities

2023

- Management of preterm, low birth weight and sick newborns
- A new approach for achieving healthy growth of infants
- Familiarization with breast milk banking (Tokyo, Japan)
- SHD for Maternal and neonatal health across Asia-Oceania Region (Tokyo, Japan)
- The implementation of new guidelines for neonatal jaundice
- Neonatal cardio pulmonary resuscitation
- KMC during newborn transport
- Start, strength and sustain KMC for every newborn everywhere

2024

- Infant obesity: causes, consequences and prevention
- Present life to the newborn
- KMC
- The new technologies for diagnosis of fetal abnormalities, prevention and treatment
- Management of preterm, low birth weight and sick newborn
- Neonatal resuscitation core instructor course

PHILIPPINES

Perinatal Association of The Philippines (PAP)

Prof. Jose B. Salazar, MD

Professor & Head of Pediatrics

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Perinatal Association of The Philippines (PAP) Highlights

- Organizes annual convention emphasizing collaboration between education and clinical practice
- Provides Continuing Professional Development (CPD) units for healthcare professionals on educations in perinatal care
- Advocates for improved maternal and child health policies, aiming to reduce maternal and infant mortality through enhanced care services
- Collaborates with various stakeholders, including government agencies and international organizations to support maternal and reproductive health initiatives
- - Promotes research and education on perinatal health contributing to the development of evidence-based practices in maternal .and neonatal healthcare.

Key Activities

2023

PAP Chapter Caravans:

- Myths and misconceptions about breastfeeding
- Sexually transmitted infection, can it affect pregnancy?
- Strengthening competency based nurse certification program towards excellent maternal & newborn care
- Hypertension in Pregnanc: Case study / Panel
- Impact of under nutrition in pregnancy to mother and newborn

Community Service:

- Community Service in Collaboration with PAP National in the Indigenous People (IP) of IRAM Resettlement Area, New Cabalan, Olongapo City. Serving 70 Families last March 31, 2023
- Community Service in Collaboration with PAP National, POPCOM, Olongapo. Serving the Indigenous People of Sitio Mampweng, Old Cabalan, Olongapo City.
 - o Giving of relief goods, hygiene kits, giving of slippers, family planning Lay Fora and Handwashing Lecture to Children – May 30, 2023, serving 85 families

Handbook:

- PAP Handbook of common perinatal emergencies and management (quick reference guide for frontline providers)

Research:

- Research with the Department of Health for the conduct of the study entitled "Assessing the Philippine Emergency Obstetrics and Newborn Care (EmONC) - A Study to Determine the Functionality of Facilities Designated to Provide BEmONC in Visayas and Mindanao," NP No. 2022-064 for implementation from April - December 2023 P

PAP Wellness Talk / Mental Wellness by Life Coach (Self Care, Retirement, etc)

Annual Convention:

- PAP 31st Annual Convention September 24-25, 2023

2024

- ORA--Operational and Review Alignment activity
- PAP leadership summit : engaging the PAP leaders
- A lenten recollection: “disconnect to reconnect during the Holy Week celebration
- conversational panel discussion on important perinatal issues

PAP Caravans:

- Hypertension / Pre-eclampsia
- Perinatal complication from hypertensive mother
- GDM
- Perinatal complication from GDM
- Nutrition in pregnancy
- Immunization for women
- PPH: The perspective from there healthcare professional
- **“PAPnership”**: a collaborative session in the virtual platform, designed in an interactive conversational panel discussion on important perinatal issues

PAP Collaborations & Convention

Collaboration with the Philippine Society of Newborn Medicine, Philippine Society of Obstetrics

& Gynaecology

- Workshop: Breastfeeding: Scorpio Training Course
- Webinar: Mother baby dialogues: Closing the gap: breastfeeding support for all - "breastfeeding is the best!"

Collaboration with the Philippine Society of Maternal Fetal Medicine

- Workshop: The EFM and pre-eclampsia workshop

Collaboration with the Philippine Society of Ob-Gyn

- Connecting communities to improve perinatal care, the 4P's: Pre-Eclampsia, PTL, PPH and Prevention For The Midwives And General Practitioner

Annual Convention: PAP 32nd Annual Convention: "Empowering Beginnings for Perinatal Care

Excellence: K PAP- Kaalamanan, Kahusayan, Kasanayan"

To effectively promote perinatal care, a multifaceted approach is essential. These include robust government initiatives, active community engagement, and collaboration among healthcare providers. These highlights of the perinatal societies of the countries Eastern Region reflect FAOPS commitment to advancing perinatal care and improving health outcomes and infants in the Asia-Oceania region. Together, these efforts will ensure the delivery of safe and effective maternal and neonatal health services.

Every action will count.

Pledge your commitment to protect MNCH needs from the impact of climate change, now, for the future.

Show your support for climate action

Reimagine your world

#HealthierTomorrow

Congenital Syphilis – A Forgotten Disease

By Sakviseth Bin, MD

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 Perinatal Society of Cambodia (PSC). Correspondence Email:
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Learning Points

- Congenital syphilis is severe but preventable with proper maternal screenings, leading to an early, timely and adequate treatment of maternal syphilis.
- Pemphigus syphiliticus is rare but pathognomonic, warranting a thorough physical examination of the newborn.
- The diagnosis tools and treatments are easily accessible and inexpensive in our economical settings.

Cambodia shares two important publications on congenital syphilis, a disease almost forgotten but remains a burden especially in many Asia-Oceania countries. The first article is a poster presented at the European Society for Paediatric Infectious Disease, and the second is a highlight of a case report of the death of a neonate with this severe but preventable condition. The preterm male infant was delivered at 30 3/7 weeks of gestational age by an emergency C-section due to placenta previa, with haemorrhage and fetal distress. The mother, 21 years old, gravida 2 parity 1, had no underlying diseases. The antenatal care was done regularly at a provincial health centre; syphilis and HIV were negative at the first prenatal visit in the first trimester. The case report illustrates a severe case of perinatal asphyxia, masking congenital syphilis. The neonate died at 32 hours of life. He required high-frequency oscillation ventilation (HFOV) and received red blood cell transfusions.

Mother-to-child transmission of *Treponema pallidum* can occur during any stage of pregnancy. Fetal infection from untreated or inadequately treated maternal syphilis can lead to serious adverse birth outcomes, including fetal loss, stillbirth, early infant death, symptomatic infected newborns, premature delivery and low birth weight. Clinical features of early congenital syphilis are variable, and the neonates are mostly asymptomatic at birth. The most common manifestations are hepatomegaly, jaundice and skin rash; other symptoms include rhinitis, lymphadenopathies, central nervous invasion and bone involvement. The full article can be found on [Bin S. BMJ Case Rep 2021;14:e246310.doi:10.1136/bcr-2021-246310](https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2021-246310)

ESPID
LIBSON & ONLINE
8-12 MAY 2023

EUROPEAN SOCIETY FOR
PAEDIATRIC INFECTIOUS DISEASES

**A SINGLE-CENTER RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY
OF CONGENITAL SYPHILIS IN A TERTIARY NICU
IN CAMBODIA DURING 48 MONTHS**

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កម្ពុជា
កម្ពុជា
កម្ពុជា
Calmette

Background:
 During COVID-19 pandemic, there was a resurgence of Congenital Syphilis (CS) in Cambodia. In our center, the first case was reported in January 2021 in spite of its absence since 2005.
 The research objectives are to determine the incidence of CS, the maternal treatment status, the newborn clinical and laboratory findings and the compliance of follow-up.

Methods:
 Type: retrospective study
 Sample: infected, inborn neonates, admitted to Neonatal ICU at Calmette Hospital
 Duration: 2 years (Jan 2021 to December 2022)
 Inclusion criteria: Congenital Syphilis (confirmed and possible), with paired serology (RPR and TPHA), using on CDC's case definition
 Exclusion criteria: stillbirths

Results:

Results:

Symptomatic	
Pemphigus	44%
Hepatomegaly	39%
Anemia	33%
Splenomegaly	22%

Figure 1 Pemphigus syphiliticus.

BIN S, BMJ Case Report, 2021		
Cases: 53	Preterm: 58.5%	Mean: 36WGA
Male: 58%	LBW: 43.4%	Mean: 2490g

Thrombocytopenia	28%	
♀ CRP (>10mg/L)	35%	Mean: 79 mg/L
Abnormal CSF	2%	

All Cases: PNC G 10 days

Death: 2%
Follow-up rate: 57%

Conclusion:
 Congenital syphilis is a global burden. However, it is preventable. The mother-to-child transmission should be and can be prevented by early diagnosis and on-time, accurate treatment of the mother by proper regimen.

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The Journey of the Bangladesh Perinatal Society

By Md. Abdul Mannan for the Bangladesh Perinatal Society.

The Bangladesh Perinatal Society (BPS) is a professional body of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Neonatologist and Pediatricians, established in 1996 which has long been providing continuous efforts for quality improvement in perinatal health and newborn health services and research in Bangladesh.

BPS been working with the Government of Bangladesh in the policy making issues of Perinatal and Neonatal Health and contributed in development of Bangladesh Neonatal Health Strategies. BPS provided their technical expertise in national scale-up of different programs in Bangladesh which includes HBB, ETAT, EPI, IMCI, IYCF, CNCP etc. BPS also has been working with different NGOs and development partners like Save the Children, WHO, UNICEF, icddr,b, USAID, alive & thrive etc.

Bangladesh Perinatal Society (BPS) has strong commitment for the improvement of perinatal health and newborn health in Bangladesh. BPS is happy to be a part of dissemination of the National Guidelines on priority newborn health interventions. BPS would like to give thank Saving Newborn Lives (SNL) Program of Save the Children for supporting this dissemination Workshop”.

The Bangladesh Perinatal Society (BPS) has been organizing the program for Celebration of World Breastfeeding Week, World Pneumonia Day, World Prematurity Day, CME, Workshop, Training, Conference and activities with Government and Development Partner. Recently Bangladesh Perinatal Society organized 4th International Scientific Conference from 8-9 May 2024. The opening ceremony was started on May 8, 2024 at 12 noon. Secretary General Professor Md. Abdul Mannan delivered a welcome speech in the opening ceremony and Professor Victor Samiul Rajadurai President, FAOPS delivered the Keynote Speech.

Founder President Professor T A Chowdhury was present as the chief guest at the inaugural function and National Professor Sahala Khatun, Professor Nazmun Nahar, Professor Mohammad Shahidullah and Professor Farhana Dewan were present as special guests. Prof. Laila Arjumand Banu presided the program and Prof. Rowshan Ara Begum delivered the vote of thanks.

Scientific session in this program were Plenary Session, Update Session, Researcher Presentation, Panel Discussion, Neonatal Ventilation Session, Policy Session, Development Partner Session, Young Researcher Presentation, Poster Presentation, Closing Ceremony.

Policy Sessions

Policy session was held in the conference on 8 May 2024 from 2 pm to 4 pm. Topic: Religiously compliant human milks storage and donation in Bangladesh- “How to overcome Challenges?”, presided over by Professor Laila Arjumand Banu and Professor Mohammad Shahidullah. Professor Ferdousi Begum moderated the program. In policy session speakers were Professor Dr. Sanjay Kumar topic- To establish breast milk bank in Bangladesh, Role of professional bodies, Dr. Md. Mozibur Rahman topic- Religiously compliant human milks storage and donation in Bangladesh- “How to overcome Challenges?”, Professor Hamijah Binte Ismail Topic- Halimatussaadia mother’s milk Centre: The first sharia-compliant human milk bank in Malaysia. and Dr. Rihab Mohammad Khader Topic- Challenges to established breast milk bank in a Muslim country Iraq.

A policy session on M-SCANU was held at the conference on 9 May 2024 from 10 am to 12 pm. In the policy session, how to establish M-SCANU in Bangladesh has been discussed in detail. The overall support of the program was provided by icddr,b. The program was presided by Prof Laila Arjumand Banu, Prof Mohammad Shahidullah and Professor Farhana Dewan. Professor Md. Abdul Mannan, was present as the speaker. Sachiya Yoshida and Dr. Md.

Zahurul Islam were the speaker.

Public Health Session:

Public Health Session was held at the conference on May 9, 2024 from 2 pm to 3 pm, presided over by Professor Hosne Ara Begum and Professor Dilruba Akhtar. Speaker were Dr. Dewan Md Emdadul Haque Topic: Investing in Maternal Health: A vital step to Lower Neonatal Mortality, Dr. Gautam Bonik Topic: Assessing the Feasibility and Effectiveness of Family Centered Care in Improving Newborn Health: A Mixed-Methods Study in Bangladesh, Dr. Arifin Amal Islam Topic: Care Companion Program: An Innovative Approach to Heighten Health Outcome and Strengthening Health Systems. and Dr. Salahuddin Ahmed Topic: PROJAHNMO'S CONTRIBUTION: MNCH Milestone Research Initiatives in Bangladesh. Foreign speakers: Secretary General Professor Dr. Md. Abdul Mannan informed the meeting that 22 foreign speakers have participated in the conference and their accommodation has been arranged at Dhaka Regency Hotel and Resort.

1. Dr. Harish Kumar Chellani (India)
2. Prof. Dr. Milind R. Shah (India)
3. Dr. Kanekal S. Gautham (Florida, US)
4. Dr. Mitesh Shetty (UK)
5. Dr. Mohit Sahni (India)
6. Dr. Rehab Mohammed Kheder (Iraq)
7. Dr. U.D.P. Ratnasiri (Sri Lanka)
8. Dr. Anand Sudhir Vinekar
9. Prof. Mamoru Tanaka (Japan)
10. Prof. Dato' Dr. Hamizah Ismail (Malaysia)
11. Dr. Azza Essa Tolba (Kuwait)
12. Prof. Dr. Ashma Rana (Nepal)
13. Dr. Kamaldeep Arora (India)
14. Dr. Surjeet Kaur Madan (India)
15. Prof. SudhinThayyil (London)
16. Prof. Victor Samuel Rajadurai (Singapore)
17. Prof. Boris W. Kramer (Netherlands)
18. Prof. Arti Maria (India)
19. Dr. Sachiyo Yoshida (Switzerland)
20. Dr. Aakash Pandita (India)
21. Dr. Arjun Chandra Dey (UK)
22. Dr. Laxmi Saha (UK)

Inauguration of 4th International Scientific Conference

Participation of Secretary General of FAOPS

Workshop on Research Methodology

Workshop on Immediate Kangaroo Mother Care (IKMC)

Closing Ceremony

Workshop on Functional Echo and POCUS for Newborn

Pre-Conference Workshop:

A total of 4 pre-conference workshops were held from 3 to 7 May 2024.

Functional ECHO workshop online on 3rd and 4th May 2024 and Practical session on 6th and 7th May 2024. In charge of this workshop Dr. Sadeka Chowdhury Moni, Dr. Md. Arif Hossain and Professor Md. Abdul Mannan.

On 04/05/2024 Small Sick Newborn Care (SSNC) workshop was held at Bangladesh Children's Hospital and Institute. In charge of this workshop Dr. Ismat Jahan and Dr. Liton Chandra Saha and Professor Maksudur Rahman.

On 05/05/2024 the Research Methodology workshop was held at Shaheed Dr. Milton Hall, BSMMU, In charge of this workshop, Dr. Mohammad Kamrul Hasan Sabuj, Dr. Shahana Akter and Prof. Sanjay Kumar Dey.

Immediate Kangaroo Mother Care (iKMC) workshop on 07/05/2024 To be held at MR Khan Children's Hospital, Mirpur-II. In charge of this workshop Professor Nabo Krishna Ghosh, Dr. Sharmin Afroze and Professor Begum Nasrin.

Workshop on Small and Sick Newborn Care in Facility

>> Climate change is one of the **gravest threats facing humanity**. **Pregnant women*, newborns and children** face distinct risks from climate change-related health impacts, due to a host of **physiological, clinical, social and behavioural factors**.

>> Climate change is a **growing threat to maternal, newborn and child health** that can no longer be ignored. With **progress stalling** on many fronts, **immediate action** is needed to meet the **Sustainable Development Goals**, with a focus on women, newborns and children.

>> **Hard-won advances** of the past decades for maternal, newborn and child survival and well-being **must be protected** to ensure the right to health for all.

Source: World Health Organization (Ed.). (2023). Protecting maternal, newborn and child health from the impacts of climate change: A call for Action. Advocacy Brief. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/374272/9789240085350-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
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The Journey of the Perinatal Society of Cambodia

By Sakviseth BIN, Sethikar IM, The Perinatal Society of Cambodia

Our Founder's Dream

H.E. Prof IM Sethikar established the Perinatal Society of Cambodia (PSC) on May 4th, 2017 in an effort to reduce neonatal and infant mortality rates in Cambodia. To this end, our mission aims to build a collective platform bestowing an opportunity upon neonatologists, obstetricians, and midwives to improve antenatal care, neonatal resuscitation, and post-natal care. Suffice it to say that PSC strives to surmount hindrances in this small, resource-limited country by virtue of stakeholders' active participation, and we dream of fostering standard first-class newborn management for future generations in Cambodia.

Materializing such a dream, the 1st Cambodian Perinatal Congress was held on November 25th, 2017. In the wake of our gradual growth, we became the 18th member of FAOPS (The Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies) on July 23rd, 2018. It is noteworthy that Prof Victor Samuel Rajadurai, the current FAOPS President, has embarked on this fruitful journey with us since the 1st Update Symposium in January 2018.

Our Activities

Over the past 8 years, our optimistic and passionate Board Members have never ceased to make continuous and consistent efforts; as a result, we have organized 5 Cambodian Perinatal Congresses, 4 Workshops, and 2 Update Symposiums. We have more than 200 nationwide and multi-disciplinary members including neonatologists, pediatricians, obstetricians, and midwives.

On October 26th, 2025, we are organizing our 6th Cambodia Perinatal Congress with the theme 'Antenatal and Perinatal Update: Reduction of Maternal and Neonatal Mortality Rate.' This congress is testimony to our continuous steps in pursuit of the betterment of perinatal care.

Our Achievements

Our Society plays an important role in the significant and continuous decline of Cambodian neonatal mortality from 27 (2010) to 18 (2014) and to only 8 per 1000 live births (2021) (Cambodia Demographic and Health Survey, 2021-2022).

Our main achievements and continuous activities include:

1. Developed national Neonatal Resuscitation Program (NRP) Workshop
2. Developed Workshop for Umbilical Venous Catheterization (UVC)
3. Published case reports and developed numerous multi-centered guidelines/researches on:
 - Antenatal steroids
 - Nutrition for Preterm infants
 - Newborn screening (Congenital hypothyroidism)
 - Perinatal infection (Neonatal sepsis and Congenital syphilis)
4. Published numerous leaflets to educate both healthcare providers and expective mothers about Nutrition during pregnancy, Kangaroo Mother Care (KMC), and Breastfeeding.

Activities in the Year 2023-2024

- A Brief Report from The Perinatal Society of Malaysia

By Dr. Neoh Siew Hong and the Perinatal Society of Malaysia

The Perinatal Society of Malaysia was established 30 years ago to encourage training and research in Perinatology in Malaysia. As a body comprising of obstetrics, fetomaternal, neonatology, paediatric nursing, public health and midwifery experts, it aims to provide expert advice to government and other bodies on matters pertaining to Perinatology, whilst maintaining liaison with other organizations, international bodies or professions involved in Perinatology.

The 30th Regional Annual Congress of the Perinatal Society of Malaysia

The 30th Regional Annual Congress of the Perinatal Society of Malaysia was held on the 14th - 17th August 2024 in the historical city of Melaka. This was the second physical congress after the Covid-19 pandemic. The theme of the congress was "Embracing SDGs: Engage, Educate & Empower". Three pre-congress workshops on Maternal Vaccination, Kangaroo Mother Care and Neonatal Lung Ultrasound received overwhelming participation. There were a total of 4 plenary lectures, 12 symposia and a forum on Planetary Health: Impact on Maternal and Neonatal Wellbeing. In addition, there were lunch symposia sponsored by industry. The faculty comprised of 9 international speakers from the UK, Singapore and Australia and 35 local speakers and facilitators. The congress was attended by 540 participants.

Nationwide webinar series

Recovering from COVID 19 Pandemic PSM continues to organise and promote educational events both physically and virtually. Five nationwide webinars via the Zoom platform delivered by international and local experts have been organised. The target participants were obstetrics, neonatal and paediatrics specialists and trainees throughout the country.

MNNR Seminar: Optimising Neonatal Care and Beyond

The Malaysian National Neonatal Registry (MNNR) under the Perinatal Society of Malaysia has successfully organized a 2-day neonatal seminar at the on 23rd - 24th September 2023 titled "Optimising Neonatal Care and Beyond" covering relevant neonatal topics. The seminar was attended by 143 participants comprising doctors and nurses working in the NICUs.

Advanced Neonatal Nutrition Seminar: Achieving Optimal Growth and Development with Optimum Nutrition

This course was held on 15th June 2024 at Grand Hyatt Hotel Kuala Lumpur in collaboration with Fresenius Kabi. The seminar was attended by 28 neonatologists, neonatal fellows and paediatricians from different states. The following topics related to the practical aspects of nutrition of the high-risk neonates were covered by 4 consultant neonatologists and a TPN pharmacist.

Comprehensive Course on Neonatal Cranial Ultrasound Screening

This course was conducted on 20th July 2024. The course aimed to enhance the knowledge and skills of healthcare professionals in neonatal cranial ultrasound screening.

With over 20 attendees from Sarawak, Ipoh, Malacca and Selangor the event featured informative

lectures, hands-on workshop and interactive sessions.

Malaysian National Neonatal Registry (MNNR)

The Malaysian National Neonatal Registry (MNNR) is founded since 2001 and was officially launched since 2004, its currently in the 20th years since launched with fifty-two source data providers (SDP) consisting of 47 Ministry of Health Hospitals, two University hospitals and three private hospitals

Based on the data from the neonatal registry, the members of the steering committee published two papers in peer reviewed journals in the year 2023-2024.

The Malaysian Neonatal Resuscitation Programme (MyNRP)

A total of 7902 providers were trained in 2023. A MyNRP National Workshop was held on the 11th December 2023. It was attended by state instructors from Ministry of Health hospitals and instructors from a few University Hospitals. The workshop also discussed the way forward for the Malaysian NRP and how to maintain standards of training. The Website for MyNRP has also been launched with providers and instructor’s login portals and teaching aids.

Upcoming events

- a) 2nd Perak Neonatal Nursing Workshop on 5th October 2024 in Ipoh, Perak
- b) PSM and UMMC are co-organising an IPOKRATES Seminar “Stabilising the sick newborn infant” on 26th - 27th November 2024 for up to 150 participants followed by “The crashing neonate – POCUS and aEEG” Workshop 28th November 2024 for a smaller number of participants. The seminar and workshop will be held in UMMC. The faculty comprises of 6 international and 2 local experts.

Stabilising the Sick Newborn Infant

Please join us for an exciting and innovative conference on stabilising sick newborn infants, which will include workshops on POCUS, aEEG, and other aspects of neuromonitoring in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

Spaces Limited and Registrations are open now!
Workshop spaces are almost full!

[Link to Registration](#)

Stabilising the Sick Newborn Infant - Conference
26-27 Nov 2024
 TJ Danaraj Auditorium
 Faculty of Medicine
 Universiti Malaya

The Crashing Neonate – Workshop
28 Nov 2024
 NICU Seminar room
 Women & Children’s Health Complex
 Universiti Malaya Medical Centre
 Kuala Lumpur
 Malaysia

Local Organisers

Secretariat - The Perinatal Society of Malaysia
 Email: perinatalocietymalaysia@yahoo.com

Dr. Azanna Ahmad Kamar
 Universiti Malaya
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Australia

Karl Schettler
Germany

Ju Lee Oei
Australia

PSANZ 2024 Congress – Whiria te Tangata “Weave our people together”

By the Perinatal Society of Australia and New Zealand (PSANZ)

Pre Congress Meetings:

Stillbirth/CRE Saturday: 64 registrations

IMPACT Saturday & Sunday: 100 registrations

Indigenous Hui: 77 registrations

Great turn out for Stillbirth CRE & IMPACT. Sessions ran well and were very engaging for attendees.

Congress Registration:

Welcome Function – 801 registrations

Monday – 912 registrations

Tuesday – 879 registrations

Wednesday – 863 registrations

Overall, it is a very impressive number for NZ Congress. Exceeded expectations and an incredible achievement for LOC. Breakfast Sessions: 1 – 42 registrations 2 – 40 registrations 3 – 29 registrations 4 – 39 registrations 5 – 38 registrations 6 – 40 registrations 7 – 39 registrations 8 – 26 registrations 9 – 40 registrations 10 – 40 registrations 11 – 36 registrations

A really good response to registration for breakfast sessions with quite an even attendance.

Abstract Submissions: Total abstracts submitted – 472 Withdrawn – 68 Oral 10 min – 79 Oral-Poster 3 min - 75 Posters Only – 246.

Abstract Sessions: The theming of abstract sessions worked really well with great attendance for each session.

PSANZ 2024 Speakers/Program & Gala Wrap Up

SPEAKERS

Invited speakers: 111 invited speakers (including consumers)

Keynote speakers: Tracy Bale, Krithika Lingappan, Nicholas Embleton, Timothy Draycott & Terri Inder.

The PROGRAM – in a snapshot

Monday 8 April

Plenary Sessions:

• Indigenous Health - Weaving the future, • Perinatal Mental Health

Symposium Sessions:

• The Whenau/Placenta and the Fetus • Culturally Safe Practice • Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia

• Infant Nutrition

Tuesday 9 April

Plenary Sessions:

• Quality & Safety

Symposium Sessions:

• Care around Stillbirth and Neonatal Death Clinical Practice Guideline: Providing culturally appropriate and safe care for parents and whānau • Rare and Complex Diseases - A Focus on Maternal Fetal Medicine

- The Preterm Brain • Best of the best from the Fetal Neonatal Workshop (Sponsored by Ritchie Centre and Monash Newborn Research) • Sexuality and intimacy issues during pregnancy and after childbirth

Wednesday 10 April

Plenary Sessions:

- Severe Growth Restriction - A Multidisciplinary Debate • Closing Plenary - Wellbeing for All

Symposium Sessions:

- The Carosika Collaborative: Achieving equity in preterm birth across Aotearoa • Research: Past, present & future • Partnering with whānau/family in the NICU • Perinatal Ethics: Shared Decision Making - Weaving Voices Together

Breakfast Sessions

Monday:

- HIE & Seizures • Eat, Sleep, Console
- PLATIPUS • Diabetes in Pregnancy

Tuesday:

- Necrotising Enterocolitis • Newborn Resuscitation • Maternal Anaemia • Implementation of Golden Hour and a Clinical Care pathway for babies born <28 weeks gestation in the NICU - A long and winding road

Wednesday:

- Long term Outcomes • Induction of Labour • Cardiomyopathy

GALA DINNER @ Te Pae Convention Centre – congress venue

Corp Comm pulled off another fantastic Gala Dinner with rave reviews from everyone who attended. The night was full of dancing, laughter, chatter and more dancing! The band was an absolute hit! Theme Flower Power – dress anything floral / flower power. It was fantastic to see all delegates dressed in an array of colour. There were many, many spins on the theme Flower Power which was great to see. Theming Kim Chan – came up with some great flower styling concepts and tailored these as requested. She created a beautiful flower wall for entrance display where delegates got to take group photos. Band & Entertainment Oval Office – booked through Christchurch Entertainment Bureau was incredible! Delegates were up and dancing as soon as the first song began and continued to dance until the very end...wanting more! Oval Office was so good we had requests from delegates to fly them out to OZ for the next PSANZ congress! Full band (at least 5 piece) and strong female vocalist.

EXTRACTS FROM PSANZ NEWSLETTER: PSANZ SUBCOMMITTEE UPDATES

AUSTRALIAN PRETERM BIRTH PREVENTION ALLIANCE (APBPA)

Education and outreach have been the guiding principles for the Australian Preterm Birth Prevention Alliance in 2024.

Fresh on the heels of the Every Week Counts National Collaborative Showcase held in the Great Hall, Parliament House, in March, key Alliance members then shifted their focus to the Torres Strait Islands.

Alliance Chair, Professor John Newnham AM, and QLD lead, Dr Chris Lehner, joined Townsville foetal maternal specialist, Dr David Watson and local doctors, for the inaugural Thursday Island Preterm Birth Prevention Workshop.

Included in the program was a sonographer's session with Dr Watson, a hands-on obstetric skills workshop including an emergency drill in birth suite, and a vaginal breech birth station run by Professor Newnham.

Thursday Island Hospital is QLD's most remote maternity service, just 60km off the PNG coast. It services 9,000 people in mostly remote Torres Strait Island communities and the North of Cape York.

The visiting contingent were very fortunate to learn about the fabulous work the Thursday Island team is doing facing many challenges in resourcing, staffing and retrieving patients from islands like Saibai and Boigu - two Queensland islands just 2km south of PNG.

More recently, Professor Newnham travelled to Bendigo for the final two events in the education series for the Safer Care Victoria Preterm Birth Prevention Education Program, hosted in conjunction with Bendigo Health.

These events, focused on promoting seven evidence-based strategies to reduce preterm and early term birth brought together over 200 maternity healthcare professionals across Loddon Mallee, Grampians, and Hume regions.

Dedicated clinicians and consumers showcased successful initiatives from their local health services, fostering a collaborative atmosphere, sharing challenges and solutions, and empowering attendees to implement similar improvements within their own health service settings.

On Friday, 14 June, the Alliance were proud to launch the 2024 edition of The Every Week Counts magazine.

This nationally distributed magazine contains features on pre-conception and pregnancy care, powerful lived experiences, and the latest from our world-first national preterm birth prevention program. This magazine is now making its way to mothers-to-be, obstetric clinics and maternity hospital across the country.

Scan the QR code or [click this link](#) to view your digital edition of the Every Week Counts Magazine

PERINATAL ETHICS (PE)

The Perinatal Ethics SIG organised one of the concurrent sessions at the Christchurch conference with a detailed discussion about ethical issues from a complex case. This session was well attended and well received.

Perinatal Ethics SIG is currently in the planning phase for their next ethics webinar, likely to be held in October 2024. The PE SIG is also planning for a workshop prior to the PSANZ congress on Sunday 16th March. Details for both the October webinar and the March workshop will be released soon.

INTERDISCIPLINARY MATERNAL PERINATAL AUSTRALASIAN COLLABORATIVE TRIALS NETWORK (IMPACT)

Save the Date
IMPACT's Two-day Concept Development Workshop is coming to Adelaide.

The Robinson Research Institute
Norwich Building 55 King William Road North Adelaide

September 6th and 7th

Do you have an idea for a perinatal clinical trial or are you interested in understanding the process of taking a trial from idea to concept?

Workshop Aims

This highly interactive and collaborative workshop aims to further support the development of maternal and perinatal clinical trials within the IMPACT Network. Held over two days, the workshop will be guided by highly experienced facilitators who will support you taking your trial from idea to fully fleshed out concept and supported by experts in all aspects of clinical trials from over Australia and New Zealand to also provide information, advice, and guidance.

Faculty

- Senior IMPACT Network members
- Expert trialists, health economics, ethics, statistics and more!
- IMPACT Network Consumer representation

Who should attend?

- Concept investigators and collaborators: bring along your team and brainstorm your concept with expert input from colleagues experienced in clinical trials design and conduct
- Emerging researchers and those wishing to observe and gain skills in the process of clinical trial development
- Consumers interested in clinical trial research in maternal and perinatal health
- Clinicians and researchers in maternal and perinatal health interested in new collaborations

Location

The Robinson Research Institute
Norwich Building 55 King William Road North Adelaide

Workshop Timing

September 6th and 7th

LIVED EXPERIENCE ADVISORY NETWORK (LEAN) (FORMALLY CAP)

Hello PSANZ,

We, LEAN, are a small group with different perinatal experiences. LEAN provides advice to PSANZ from a lived experience perspective and offers participation in PSANZ subcommittees and activities.

This year, the Board and LEAN are working to grow the network within PSANZ. As such, we're seeking expressions of interest from those who may be interested in joining LEAN in the near future. To help us grow the network, please share this news with people that you work with who may be interested in joining LEAN. Families and carers with perinatal lived experience can register their interest in joining LEAN via the PSANZ website: https://PSANZ.formstack.com/forms/eoi_psanz_subcommittee_lean

Thank you,

- Nat, Kelly, Amanda, Melinda and Kylie
LEAN members

LONG-TERM OUTCOMES OF HIGH-RISK BABIES (LOHB)

PSANZ 2024 highlights

We were delighted to host the breakfast session (10th April) on behalf of our Long-term Outcomes of High-risk Babies Subcommittee (LOHB) during PSANZ 2024 in Christchurch. We were lucky to have Assoc Prof Malcolm Battin and parent representative Jenn Hopper to lead this session and was chaired by our LOHB members Dr Lisa Kremer and Dr Manbir Chauhan.

Here is some feedback kindly shared by Jenn Hopper.

"Hi Jenn, I just listened to your talk and came up to you at the end with a child with Autism and ADHD... We work in a level 2 SCBU in Nelson. A lot of our work is around the NE pathway and I think your lived experience would be amazing... Thank you for everything you do and having the greatest impact on me from PSANZ."

"I think it was an enormously helpful presentation that was both very real and insightful in identifying every day challenges."

"Kia ora Jenn, I recently attended your talk at the PSANZ conference. Thank you so much for sharing your life and the realities of your care for your beautiful daughter. I learned so much from your talk (and was pretty tearful sitting in the back row).

I am a paediatric and neonatal registrar and involved with supporting other registrars through their clinical exams. One of the goals of the clinical exams is to ensure that registrars gain an understanding of the experiences of whanau caring for children with complex health needs. They need to learn about many of the topics you spoke on including transition, funding and legal issues, schooling, puberty and growth, community support available, the impact on families, and practicalities of care (like your genius medication solution!)."

PSANZ 2025 - BRISBANE, QLD, AUSTRALIA

Hello and welcome!

We are delighted to invite you to Brisbane (Meeanjin), Queensland, Australia, for the annual PSANZ Congress. This year's theme is 'Navigating Futures Together'.

The congress will be held at the Brisbane Convention & Exhibition Centre, nestled within the beautiful south Brisbane region, close to the Southbank parklands and cultural precincts. Pre-congress meetings will be held on the 14-16 March, and the main event on the 16-19 March.

Our theme, 'Navigating Futures, Together,' represents the often-uncharted road we take as perinatal researchers, clinicians, and consumers toward new knowledge to drive improvements and reform in perinatal health. It also speaks to the journey of the woman, navigating her new future as a mother with a newborn and all that is represented for the families who remain at the heart of all we do.

Our congress logo was created by Bindi Lee Day, a proud Quandamooka Noonuccal woman. Entitled 'Borning', the artwork is a modern interpretation of the development, importance, and spiritual significance of the 'Borning' journey from pregnancy to birthing to motherhood (more information below). This resonates beautifully with the PSANZ mission to improve the health and long-term outcomes for mothers and babies.

Our program will honour this theme through a diverse range of speakers, workshops, panels, and Q&A sessions – all intended to energise our perinatal community toward further advancements.

Brisbane and the surrounding region offer a vibrant culture and landscape to explore. Our River City and perinatal community would like to warmly welcome you in 2025.

On behalf of the local organising committee,

Associate Professor Lauren Kearney & Dr Christoph Lehner
Chairs, PSANZ 2025 Brisbane, Australia

WEBSITE

VENUE

25th Year of Publication

The Journey of a Journal: Perinatology

Journal of Perinatal and Neonatal Care

By Ranjan Pejaver, Professor of Neonatology, Chief Neonatologist, People tree @Meenakshi Hospital, Bangalore, India.

It was in 1996 that I returned to India (city of Bangalore.) after my stints in Harare, UK, and the Middle east. What struck me was that there was still a feeling that the obstetricians, were in charge until the delivery and then the paediatricians (neonatologists.). It was very well known that for a better outcome of mother and the baby, these professionals should liaise right from the antenatal period. In some cases, even before conception. A newborn is just a continuum of the fetus. I started this journal with a purpose of bringing these two groups together and many more like fetal medicine specialists, ultrasonologists, geneticists, nurses and all others who are involved in the care of mother and newborn. It has acted as a platform for disseminating the concept of Perinatal medicine.

- ◆ One of the very few journals exclusive to the field of perinatal medicine.
- ◆ Under the able leadership of the chief editor Dr Ranjan Kumar Pejaver and the managing editor Dr Jayashree B Keshav, the journal has successfully completed 24 years of publication and is in its Silver Jubilee year.
- ◆ Print copies are distributed to about 9,000 doctors every quarter (before the COVID-19 pandemic to 14000 doctors).
- ◆ Publication protocol and quality are on par with that of several reputed journals from various countries across the globe.
- ◆ Digital presence through the journal's website and Scientific Publication Mobile App.
- ◆ Does not carry any product advertisements nor has the Himalaya (sponsors) branding in the entire journal.
- ◆ There are no page charges for publishing articles in Perinatology
- ◆ Subscription to the print format of the journal is also free of cost
- ◆ Full-text pdfs of articles can be downloaded from the journal's website free of cost.

Founder Editor in chief:
Dr Ranjan Kumar Pejaver.

Managing Editor:
Dr Jayashree Keshav

- **Perinatology**-Journal of Perinatal and Neonatal Care - **25th year of publication.**
- **first journal in India in the field of perinatal medicine and proud to be amongst only a handful of journals, in the world**
- **Indexed in Scopus, Embase/exerpta Medica Cinhal databses. Soon in Pubmed.**
- **Digital presence through the journal's website and Scientific Publication Mobile App**
- **Received articles from 40 countries.**
- **Published by Himalaya.**

At this juncture I would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to all who encouraged and helped me in this Journey of The Journal and request you all to continue to do so.

Doctor Turns Writer: The Heaven as I Saw

Ranjan Pejaver, Professor of Neonatology, Chief Neonatologist, People tree @Meenakshi Hospital, Bangalore, India.

FAOPS would like to share the good news that a past president of FAOPS, Dr. Ranjan Pejaver, Professor of Neonatology has released his first English novel, 'The Heaven as I Saw', both as paper back and e- book.

It has received a Google review rating of 4.6 out of 6. The inspiring book is definitely read-worthy. The book is available via Amazon at the following website.

<https://www.amazon.com/Heaven-as-I-Saw/dp/8119355121>

Congratulations Dr. Ranjan Pejaver!

Dr Ranjan Pejaver, is a renowned Pediatrician and Neonatologist. Dr Ranjan Pejaver has to his credit, more than 30 books, 150 scientific papers in his speciality. An Innovator and researcher, he is an eminent speaker and a sought-after teacher. He is a well-travelled person.

"The Heaven as i Saw" is a thoughtful, imaginative take on life; or rather, life soon after death! In his first non-medical book, the author, Dr Ranjan Pejaver, has deftly handled the most unusual theme, holding the readers' attention all the while.

Dr Pejaver's earthy and penetrative novel reminds me of Jataka Tales from my childhood. Each story within the larger canvas interrogates questions of morality and ethics in modern society.

Amandeep Sandhu, Writer and Journalist

A most unusual journey, and accidental one at that. Unmasking happens of reputations and the hero gains wisdom through this trip. Could be quite inspiring for the reader. Congratulations, Dr Ranjan on your first novel

*Ajit Bhilde, literature enthusiast
Psychiatrist and Psychotherapist*

Fiction

ISBN 9788119355124

Dorpon

INR 295.00

PERINASIA Charity Program 2023 for Underdeveloped Area Program to “Reduce Neonatal Morbidities and Mortality”

– Report on Project Implementation

By Dr. Setyadewi Lusyati for PERINASIA, Indonesia.

Background

Neonatal mortality is still high in Indonesia, caused by prematurity (44%), infection, asphyxia (39%), and congenital anomalies.

It can be reduced by increasing the competence of human resources, adequate and appropriate equipment, and the structured aim of a management system based on the area.

To help overcome this problem, PERINASIA conducted training activities for health providers, especially in areas rarely reached by the PERINASIA program, including training on helping babies' Breathing (HBB) and neonatal stabilization.

We chose 4 LOCATIONS that were rarely or not yet reached by the PERINASIA program:

1. Belitung (Bangka Belitung province)
2. Banjarbaru (South Kalimantan province)
3. Tomohon (North Sulawesi province)
4. Kendari (Southeast Sulawesi province)

Objectives

- To improve the quality of health service performance in neonatal health:
- To improve the skills and confidence of midwives to help babies who have difficulty breathing at birth (asphyxia)
- To introduce the HBB program and produce trainers in the area, which has yet to be reached by the HBB program.
- To improve the skills of health providers in assessing and stabilizing sick babies after resuscitation or before referral (capacity building).

Time of Activities

Training program	Belitung	Banjarbaru	Tomohon	Kendari	
	Provider course	Provider course	Training of Trainer (TOT)	Provider course	Provider course
HELPING BABIES BREATHE (HBB)	May 31 & June 1, 2023	July 5-6, 2023	July 18-19, 2023	July 20-21, 2023	August 19-20, 2023
NEONATAL STABILIZATION (STABLE)	May 31 & June 1, 2023	July 7-8, 2023		July 16-17, 2023	Sep 23-24, 2023

The main activities of this project were carried out in 4 locations and we are grateful that everything went well. A total of 311 participants have benefited from the training programme. The response from the training participants was excellent and this can be seen in their assessment of providing feedback on the training process. This activity had allowed us to meet many health workers in distant areas and share knowledge.

Conclusion

The organizing committee from the Indonesian Midwives Association and regional hospitals have worked very well and appreciate this programme. We would like to express our high appreciation to the LDSC & FAOPS for their all support in helping babies in Indonesia.

Whose Voice, Whose Suffering

By Azanna Ahmad Kamar, Associate Professor of Neonatology,
Universiti Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

I heard my mother's voice today,
She sobbed, a little whimper,
You will suffer my child, you will not be perfect,
You were born too soon, with a bleed in the brain,
No longer normal, no longer perfect,
Imperfections will make you suffer, o' my little one.
So cruel is the world, not accepting such imperfections,
So intimidating is the world, survive and you'll suffer,
So difficult is the world, survive and we'll suffer,
Will I be able to support you, can I watch you suffer, will we suffer?
Please leave to your place in the heavens, o' my little one.

I heard my mother's voice today,
She spoke gently in a whisper,
Why did they save you my little one? You survived!
Why did you not go to heaven my little one? You are alive!
You were born too soon, with a bleed in the brain,
No longer normal, no longer perfect,
Imperfections will make you suffer, o' my little one.
You aren't perfect and will not be accepted, for the world is too cruel,
You will face the intimidating world, you will suffer,
You will live in the difficult world, and we will suffer,
I can't support you my child, I can't watch you suffer, we will suffer,
For your place should've been in the heavens. Not the world, my little one.

As hours became days, As I breathed on my own,
As the difficult, intimidating world becomes my place,
My place to suffer? Not!
I was born too soon, with a bleed in the brain,
The doctors saved me, and I am alive!
My place is in the world, not yet the heavens, dear mother.
I know not if I will suffer, as I cry for milk in a voice so loud,
I know not if we will suffer, as I cry for a cuddle my dear mother,
The voice of fate which we do not know of,
The voice of the world's kindness which we do not know of,
To suffer? I know, it's not now, dear mother.
My place is in this world, to endure, to cherish,
I am not perfect, with a bleed in the brain,
just not yet the heavens, dear mother, the fate which we do not know of,
my place is with you, mother.

The Journal of Perinatal Society of Nepal

The Perinatal Society of Nepal

This journal JPESON is a biennial (Sept /March) journal of PERINATAL SOCIETY OF NEPAL, established in 1997 and is basically conceptualized to motivate more people in scientific write-up by providing opportunities for publication of scientific work. It intends to introduce correct path to publication for beginners and hope to maintain very few rejection rate, by friendly suggestion and better encouragement.

The team JPESON Team kindly requests your contributions and if you have any completed articles related to perinatology, please kindly mail us at editorjpeson2022@gmail.com

Looking forward to your submission

Thanking you

Prof Dr. Ashma Rana & Prof. Dr Sunil Raja Manandhar
for team JPESON

<https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/2976-1050>

The banner for the 24th Congress of the Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies (FAOPS 2025) is set against a dark blue background with a white border. On the left is the circular logo of the Federation of the Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies. The central text reads 'FAOPS 2025' in large white letters, with 'The 24th Congress of the Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies' written below it. To the right is a circular graphic of a mountain range with a sun and a person. Below the main text is the theme: 'Innovation and Integration: Shaping the future of Perinatal Care in Asia and Oceania'. At the bottom, the dates 'NOVEMBER 14-16 2025' and the location 'KATHMANDU NEPAL' are displayed, accompanied by a calendar icon and a location pin icon. A small floral graphic is at the bottom center.

FAOPS 2024 Council Members

Position	Name
President	Dr. Victor Sam Rajadurai, Singapore
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President Elect	Dr. Han Suk Kim, Korea
Secretary General	Dr. Milind Shah, India
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West	Dr. Abdul Mannan, Bangladesh
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Committee on Scientific & Training Activities	Dr. Te Fu Chan, Taiwan
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Past-President, FAOPS 2004	Dr. T'sang T'ang Hsieh, Taiwan
Past-President, FAOPS 1998	Dr. Victor Yu, Philippines

FAOPS Website

<https://faopsperinatal.org/>

PUBLISHED September 4, 2024

Known effects and impacts of climate change on health

DIRECT

INDIRECT

Temperature extremes

Rising sea levels and salination

Floods and drought

Windstorms and wild fires

Ambient air pollution

Threats to livelihoods and human rights

Displacement and migration

Weakened health systems and infrastructure

Impacts on food and water systems

Infectious and vector-borne diseases

Exacerbation of social determinants and inequalities

Adapted from Etzel RA, Weimann E, Homer C et al. The impacts of climate change across the life course. (unpublished)

Source: World Health Organization (Ed.). (2023). Protecting maternal, newborn and child health from the impacts of climate change: A call for Action. Advocacy Brief. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/374272/9789240085350-eng.pdf?sequence=1> ISBN: 978 92 4 008535 0 <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/374272/9789240085350-eng.pdf?sequence=1>